

The decision

Science plays a very important role in the development of new treatments and medicines for dentistry. Without scientific research, testing to determine the positive and negative effects of new proposals would not be possible, which would lead to ineffective and possibly harmful treatments being performed. Science is now more evident in the world of dental health, with companies launching new products based on scientific tests in the market. The range of these products is due in large part to advances in science, technology and innovation. Dentists have welcomed the advances in oral hygiene products and the dissemination of new surgical techniques. We recommend certain types of products for specific ailments and exercise clinical actions to restore health. The key is the decision.

All decisions in dentistry are based on the beliefs and values of those who decide them. Science can and should help those who decide, giving support to their beliefs. Unfortunately, science is not easily accessible to those who face decisions¹. Science doesn't exist if you don't communicate, so it is necessary to expand its broadcasting tools. It is here, in this year where our own decision emerges and the beginning of what we hope are many texts move forward with a new name. In order to increase access to dental scientific knowledge, thereby improving the quality of our profession and decision-making, we are presented with Mouth, the dental journal (ISSN 0719-7659).

Mouth is an open access journal, reviewed by qualified peers, dedicated to the dissemination of ideas, opinions and clinical, practical and scientific aspects related to the oral cavity. We want to stimulate interest and discussion of colleagues from all specialties, along with collaborating in the process of continuing education. Sharing a passion for improving the quality of odontology is the intention, since its inception our journal is the official organ of scientific diffusion of South Dental Group of Continuing Education (GECOS).

Our launch is an opportunity to celebrate the beginning of the realization of a project of illusions. We believe that the growing national and international dental activity needs of a greater

number of paths of dissemination for knowledge to reach a greater number of colleagues and students. Mouth also provides an opportunity in the improvement of the curriculum, since the publication of scientific articles is a requirement that emerges more strongly, as the workforce becomes more rigorous and competitive.

To facilitate dissemination and productivity of our audience, we have arranged some initial sections, to which we will gradually be adding. The opinion category expects to receive letters from colleagues expressing views. The news section will discuss relevant aspects of the dental industry and will update on the latest developments related to the journal. The practice category is responsible for receiving relevant reports from different specialists, aimed at improving dental practice. The research section will be responsible for the eminent broadcasting of scientific communications, in the form of letters to the editor, case reports, literature reviews and original research. The images category greatly excites us, as this is where classic images of common dental conditions will be published. Finally, the posters section will receive panels and boards presented at international and national conferences.

Deciding to launch the journal is a challenge and the result of a lot of hard work discipline. Certainly, the most complicated process will ensure their maintenance and permanence, as well as bringing together authors to give life to this creation. The Internet has provided free global availability of scientific journal articles², and we hope this engine allows for the expansion of our publishing machine. Dear colleagues and students, we extend the invitation to share your knowledge and experiences with us.

César Rivera, BDentSc, DDS, MSc
Editor
Mouth

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.154280

REFERENCES

1. von Winterfeldt D. Bridging the gap between science and decision making. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2013;110 Suppl 3:14055-14061.
2. Bjork BC, Welling P, Laakso M, Majlender P, Hedlund T, Gudnason G. Open access to the scientific journal literature: situation 2009. *PLoS One*. 2010;5:e11273.

Mouth
ISSN 0719-7659
Curicó, Región del Maule, Chile

twitter.com/mouthcomms
facebook.com/mouthcomms
instagram.com/mouthcomms